

Emotional Intelligence and Its Effect on Leadership Effectiveness of First-Line Nurse Managers

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Abstract: Emotional intelligence plays a key role in leadership effectiveness and might promote effectiveness at all levels in organizations. Effective leaders with high emotional intelligence might facilitate the individuals they lead to raise their own level of emotional intelligence, potentially resulting in a more effective organization overall and a better organizational climate. Aim of the study: assessing effect of emotional intelligence on the first-line nurse managers' leadership effectiveness. Design: A descriptive correlational research design. Setting: Ain Shams University Hospitals. Subjects: (80) first-line nurse managers. Tools of data collection: Emotional intelligence questionnaire, and Leadership effectiveness questionnaire. Result: Majority of first-line nurse managers had low total emotional intelligence level and leadership ineffectiveness level. Additionally, there were highly statistically significance correlation between emotional intelligence and leadership effectiveness score among first-line nurse managers. Conclusion: The level of emotional intelligence and leadership effectiveness was low among first-line nurse managers. Also, there was highly statistically significance correlation between total emotional intelligence score and total leadership effectiveness score Recommendations: developing training program that enhance emotional intelligence competencies, and improve leadership effectiveness for first-line nurse managers.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, First-line nurse managers, Leadership effectiveness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence plays a key role in leadership effectiveness and might promote effectiveness at all levels in organizations. Effective leaders with high emotional intelligence might facilitate the individuals they lead to raise their own level of emotional intelligence, potentially resulting in a more effective organization overall and a better organizational climate. The managing own emotions subscale was significantly correlated with the effectiveness outcome on the leadership subscale. This supports the assumption that leadership effectiveness could have its roots in managing emotions (*Dabke, 2016*).

Emotional Intelligence is the ability to observe one's own and other's thinking and actions. It embodies associate individual's ability to understand emotions accurately, appraise, and categorize them; the power to come up with feelings that facilitate thoughts; the ability to know emotion and regulate emotions to push emotional and intellectual growth (*Perkins, 2018*). Moreover, Understanding emotions branch provides data to the leaders regarding however the subordinate behaves, and the way he/she is affected by environment and relationships. They'll be a lot of receptive followers' view points and anticipate their reactions in varied things. What, is more managing emotions could facilitate help the leader to focus on problem-solving, empower the followers, and create an atmosphere of enthusiasm and positive energy (*Edelman and Knippenberg, 2018*).

Leadership effectiveness is seen as the leader's influence and ability to successfully exercise personal influence on others, thereby resulting leading to the attainment of set goals and objectives. leadership effectiveness involved with the power to change by setting dynamic purpose and direction, and a peace force and create work system during which individuals

address problems and opportunities with creative thinking and commitment, in order that the organization achieve its objectives. Leadership effectiveness has been delineating additionally as associating level of confidence with the knowledge, skills and abilities related to with leading others (*Matheri et al., 2018; Adiguzel, 2019*). Furthermore, Effective leaders use their emotions to convey their messages. Once leaders feel excited, enthusiastic and active, they'll be additional probably to energize their subordinates and convey a sense of efficacy, competence, optimism, and enjoyment so, successful leaders are emotionally intelligent (*Bevis, 2019*).

First line nurse managers plays pivotal role in the lives of their staff and essential in ensuring quality patient outcomes, they have the responsibility to assure that the mission of the organization is translated into every day practice, while assuring the quality and efficiency of the daily operations of their unit. These complicated roles and responsibilities are necessary and can be applied if successfully well trained (*Gibb et al., 2018*).

Significance of study:

The researcher observed that some of first-line nurse managers don't understand their subordinates feelings and emotions, they don't caring about their subordinates' personal and work problems and don't seek to solve it and they can't make successful relationships with their subordinates. There had reflections on staff performance, quality of care rendering to the patient and the effectiveness of first-line nurse manager's role in their work unit.

So, the present study will be carried out as an attempt to improve first-line nurse managers' emotional intelligence that will lead to improve leadership effectiveness of them

Aim of the stud

This study aims at assessing the effect of emotional intelligence on the first-line nurse managers' leadership effectiveness.

Research question:

Is there a relationship between emotional intelligence and leadership effectiveness among first-line nurse managers?

2. SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Research design:

a. A descriptive correlational study design was used in the conduction of this study.

b. Setting:

The study was conducted at five hospitals affiliated to Ain Shams University Hospitals. These Hospitals namely Ain Shams University Hospital, El-Demerdash Hospital, Paediatrics Hospital, Obstetrics, and Gynaecology Hospital and Cardiovascular hospital. These Hospitals serve a large sector of the population and offer medical and surgical care in various specialties in addition to emergency services.

c. Subjects:

The study subjects included (80) first-line nurse managers out of (120) working in the previously mentioned setting. First line nurse managers were selected by using simple random technique.

d. Tools of data collection:

Data for this study were collected using two tools namely: Emotional intelligence questionnaire, and Leadership effectiveness questionnaire.

First tool:

Emotional intelligence questionnaire. It was adopted from (*Mohamed et al., 2016*).It aimed to assess emotional intelligence level among first-line nurse managers. It consisted of two parts:

Part 1: This part was concerned with the demographic characteristics of the study subjects, such as age, gender, marital status, name of the hospital, work unit, nursing qualification, and years of work experience and previous attendance of training course.

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Part II: It contains (82) items grouped under five dimensions as follow (self-awareness, self -regulation, self -motivation, empathy and social skills).

Scoring system: First-line nurse managers' responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranged from “1= never to 5= always”. The scores of items were summed-up and the total divided by number of the items. These scores were converted into a percent score. In addition, the calculation of the mean and standard deviation was done. Emotional intelligence level was considered low if the total score was less than 60% and high if the total score was 60% or more (*El gazer, 2014*).

Second tool: Leadership effectiveness questionnaire: It was developed by (*Guillen and Florent, 2011*). It was translated into Arabic and back retranslated by the researcher. It aimed to assess leadership effectiveness of first-line nurse managers. It contains fifty items grouped under six dimensions as follows: Envisioning, energizing, designing and aligning, rewarding, team-building, and empowering.

Scoring system: First-line nurse managers' responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree”. The scores of items were summed-up and the total divided by number of the items. These scores were converted into a percent score. In addition, the calculation of the mean and standard deviation was done. Leadership considered ineffective if the percent score was less than 60% and effective if total score 60% or more (*Pfeiffer, 2005*).

Validity of study tools were validated by experts group who consisted of nine teaching staff from different faculties of nursing specialized in nursing administration and psychiatric nursing. The expert members were consisted of one professor of psychiatric nursing and two professors of nursing administration from faculty of nursing, Ain Shams University, Two assistant professors and one professor of nursing administration, two professors and one assistant professor of psychiatric nursing, El-Menoufia University. Expert group members judged the tools for comprehensiveness, accuracy, and clarity in language (face validity). While the expert group members judged the importance of items to be included in the tools (content validity). Based on their recommendation corrections, addition and / or

II. Operational design

The operational design includes the preparatory phase, pilot study, and the field work.

a. Preparatory phase

This phase started with a review of current and past, national and international related literature concerning the subjects of the study, using textbooks, articles, journals, and websites.

Pilot study

The pilot study was carried out on 10% of the study sample (8 first line nurse managers). These eight first line nurse managers were included in the main study sample. Data obtained from the pilot study was analyzed, and no modifications were done. The time consumed for fulfilling the study tools was 20 minutes.

Fieldwork

The actual field work of the study was started from middle of April to the middle June, and took about 8 week (2 days/week). The researcher took permission from the hospital directors both medical and nursing, after explaining the aim of the study to gain their approval and support. The researcher met the subjects to explain the purpose of the study and ask for their participation. The researcher met the respondents either individually or groups during all shifts to distribute the questionnaire during these meetings. The study tools were distributed. The filled forms were handed back to the researcher to check each one to ensure its completeness.

III. Administrative design: Before embarking on the study, official letter was obtained from the Faculty of Nursing, Ain-Shams University to the director of the study setting. It included the aim of the study, and the expected benefits. It ensured confidentiality of the information obtained.

IV. Statistical Design: Data were presented using descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies and percentages for qualitative variables, and means $\pm$ standard deviations for quantitative variables. Qualitative variables were compared using chi-square test. T-test was used for comparisons between two-independent quantitative variables. Pearson correlation co-

efficient (r) was used for assessment of the inter-relationship among quantitative variables. The confidence level chosen for the study was 95%. Statistical significance was considered at p value <0.05.

3. RESULTS

Table (1) shows that, approximately half (50.0%) of first-line nurse managers had age ranged between 35-45 years old. Moreover, majority of first-line nurses' managers were female. Slightly more than three quarters (77.5%) of first-line nurse managers had nursing diploma. Almost half (50.0%) of first-line nurse managers had experience in current position between 10-20 years.

Table (2) reveals that, the personal competencies dimension got the highest mean score (88.66±13.72) among first-line nurses' managers regarding emotional intelligence. While, the empathy dimension had the lowest mean score (20.98±3.97).

Fig (1) shows that, majority (87.5%) of first-line nurse managers had low total emotional intelligence level.

Table (3) reveals that, the team-building dimension got the highest effective mean score (20.15±4.65) among first-line nurse managers regarding leadership effectiveness. While, designing and aligning dimension had the lowest effective mean score (11.40±2.77).

Fig (2) shows that, majority (85.0%) of first-line nurse managers had ineffective total leadership effectiveness level.

Table (4) shows that, there was highly statistically significance correlation between total emotional intelligence score and total leadership effectiveness score among first-line nurse managers.

Table (1): Distribution of study subjects demographic characteristic and work place (n= 80).

Items	First-line nurse managers	
	Frequency	Percent
Age (in Years)		
< 35	16	20.0
35-45	40	50.0
>45	24	30.0
Mean ± SD	38.28±6.14	
Range	28-50	
Gender		
Male	4	5.0
female	76	95.0
Nursing qualification		
Diploma	62	77.5
Specialty diploma	0	0.0
Bachelor	18	22.5
Experience		
< 10years	18	22.5
10- 20 years	40	50.0
> 20years	22	27.5
Mean ± SD	2.05 ±0.71	
Experience in current position		
< 10years	18	22.5
10- 20 years	40	50.0
> 20years	22	27.5
Mean ± SD	2.43 ±0.76	
Training programs		
Yes	80	100.0
No	0	0.0

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Table (2): First-line nurses managers’ total emotional intelligence scores (n= 80).

Emotional intelligence dimensions	First-line nurses managers
	Mean ± SD
Self-awareness	26.40±7.32
Self-regulation	29.80±5.96
Self-Motivation	32.45±3.87
personal competencies	88.66±13.72
Empathy	20.98±3.97
Social skills	42.75±8.18
social competencies	63.73±10.72
Total emotional intelligence	152.38±22.64

Fig (1): Percentage distribution of total emotional intelligence level among First-line nurses managers.

Table (3): First-line nurses managers’ total emotional intelligence scores (n= 80).

Leadership effectiveness dimensions	First-line nurses managers
	Mean ± SD
Envisioning	15.35±3.45
Energizing	14.05±3.37
Designing and Aligning	11.40±2.77
Rewarding and Feedback	14.28±3.18
Team-Building	20.15±4.65
Empowering	14.30±3.78
Total leadership effectiveness	89.53±12.46

Fig (2): Percentage distribution of total leadership effectiveness level among first-line nurses managers.

Table (4): Correlations between total emotional intelligence score and total leadership effectiveness score among

Parameter	Total emotional intelligence score	
	r	P-value
Total knowledge regarding emotional intelligence score	0.636	<0.000**

4. DISCUSSION

Recent theories emphasize that effective leadership is affected by the personality of the leader, general conditions in the workplace and the quality characteristics of employees. From this perspective, the fact that the EI has made a significant contribution to leadership effectiveness becomes one of the key characteristics of leaders. In addition emotionally intelligent leaders with an administrative position inspire emotions, passion and motivation helping thus to achieve goals that might otherwise have not been conquered (*Panagiotis, 2018*).

According to the study finding, the mean score of personal competencies among first line nurses managers was the highest one. This finding may be due to a strong sense of self, and self-confident of first line nurses managers, also their ability to understand and regulate their feelings and emotions. This result was supported by a study done at Zagazig University by *Mohamed (2012)*, who mentioned that, the highest mean score among first line nurses managers was personal competencies.

On other hand, the present study showed that, social competencies had the lowest mean score among first line nurses managers. This finding may be due to they didn't perceived greater strengths in social skills and utilization of emotions, management of emotions and empathy, and in practical abilities. In contrary with the study finding a study conducted at University of Victoria by *John and Astronaut, (2015)*, who stated that the participants had higher scores for social competencies

Also, majority of first-line nurse managers had low total emotional intelligence level. From the researcher point of view this could be due to low awareness of first line nurses managers about emotional intelligence and absence of training courses and activities that help to improve emotional intelligence skills. In agreements with the study finding a study conducted in Aga central hospital at Mansoura city by *Mohamed et al., (2016)* who reported that, less than one fifth of nursing leaders had high total emotional intelligence. In the same line *Vesely et al. (2014)*, who concluded that, managers had low satisfactory level in total emotional intelligence.

The finding of the present study clarified that, the mean score of team-building dimension among first line nurses managers was the highest one. This finding could be due to first line nurse managers were empathic and had high levels of teamwork skills. These finding was in agreements with *Lee et al. (2018)*, who reported that, participants were empathic and had high levels of teamwork skills.

Also, the present study finding showed that, the mean score of designing and aligning, rewarding and feedback dimensions was ineffective leadership level. This finding could be due to emotional intelligence influence the effectiveness of leadership

skills and practice. In agreements with this finding a study was done in Malaysia by *Singh et al. (2012)*, who found that, a significance positive correlation between emotional intelligence and effectiveness of leadership skills and practice.

In addition, the present study finding showed that, majority of first-line nurse managers had ineffective leadership level. This finding may be due to absence of leadership development program, that improve leadership practice and skills, and insist of training department continue to focus on traditional knowledge and skills. In agreements with the study finding, by *Naïem (2014)*, who mentioned that, the highest percentage of study sample had unsatisfactory scores of leadership effectiveness.

Also, the present study showed that, there were highly statistically significance correlation between total emotional intelligence score and total leadership effectiveness score among first-line nurse managers. This may be due to emotional intelligence contributes to people's capacity to work effectively in teams, manage stress, and lead others effectively. In addition, emotional intelligence helps in improving leadership and performance, thus affects leaders effectiveness. In agreements with study finding a study done at Egypt by *Nabih et al. (2016)*, who found that, emotional intelligence has a strong positive and significant relationship with leadership effectiveness. Also, *Bano (2013)*, who reported that, implementation of emotions intelligent in any organization by a leader to be effective and efficient, plays a vital role to leader effectively.

5. CONCLUSION

According to the study findings, it can be concluded that, the mean score of personal competencies among first line nurses mangers was the highest one. On other hand social competencies had the lowest mean score. Moreover, majority of first-line nurse managers had low total emotional intelligence level. Majority of first-line nurse managers had ineffective leadership level. The mean score of team-building dimension among first line nurses mangers was the highest one, while the mean score of designing and aligning had the lowest effective mean score. Additionally, there were highly statistically significance correlation between emotional intelligence score and leadership effectiveness score.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the main study findings, the following recommendations were deducted:

- Health sector must fully understand the importance of emotional intelligence and first line nurse managers should be trained in the best ways of applying emotional intelligence practices.
- The training department and the human resource department of the organizations should think about the different training methods to enhance emotional intelligence levels whereby they can improve leadership qualities.
- Orientation program for first line nurse managers have to include emotional intelligence and leadership practice.
- Developing training program that enhance emotional intelligence competencies, and improve leadership effectiveness for first-line nurse managers.

Further studies are suggested:

- Impact of emotional intelligence program on leadership skills among nursing leaders.
- Relationship between emotional intelligence and decision making among nurse leaders.

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